

Voluntary business-to-government data sharing to address societal challenges: exploring actor alignment to create mutual benefits

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Keywords: B2G-data-sharing; public-private-partnerships; incentives; actor-alignment; mutual-benefits.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the complexity and scope of societal challenges, coordinated joint efforts between public and private organisations (public-private partnerships) are crucial in addressing them (e.g. Brinkerhoff & Brinkerhoff, 2011; George et al., 2016; Kuhlmann & Rip, 2018; Mazzucato, 2018). Within public-private partnerships literature, data sharing recently gained a more prominent role, as its potential to address societal challenges is increasingly recognized by public sector organisations (e.g. Verhulst et al, 2019; Susha et al, 2019a).

As a result, *data collaboratives* and namely Business-to-Government data sharing initiatives that aim to address societal challenges gained more attention in the literature on public-private data sharing. Their cross-sectoral nature makes it beneficial for governmental organisations to participate, as privately held data can complement the available public data to gain a deeper, multi-perspectival understanding of a societal challenge (Robin, Klein & Jütting, 2016). The benefits for the private sector, however, are less straightforward. In order for data collaboratives to scale up and move their practices forward, Business-to-Government (B2G) data sharing for the public interests needs to be mutually beneficial and sustainable (EC, 2020).

Academic literature reiterates the need to understand the drivers and motivations of B2G data sharing in order to advance this practice of data collaboratives further (Susha et al., 2017, Susha et al., 2019a; Rukanova et al., 2020). Furthermore, it is argued that data collaboratives need to find win-win scenarios and balance the interests of public and private actors (Ruijter, 2021; Susha et al., 2019b; Klein & Verhulst, 2017; Klievink & Janssen, 2012). Although this need is recognized, limited knowledge is available on how this can be done in a B2G data sharing context. This study addresses this research gap and explores the following research question: *how can voluntary B2G data sharing to address societal challenges be mutually and sustainable?*

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The main concepts of interest for this research are: actor's interests, alignment of interests, and benefits/value creation. The framework for voluntary B2G information sharing by Rukanova et al. (2020) has been used as a starting point in this study. The framework contends that B2G data sharing between government and business is influenced by policy, technological, and organisational factors and introduces the concept of *alignment of interests as part of the governance processes*. The framework of Rukanova et al. (2020) provides a basic view of these, yet further elaboration is needed. To elaborate on Rukanova et al. (2020), this research adopted the view of Selsky & Parker distinguishing between organisational self-interest and societal interest of partners in B2G data sharing. Furthermore, to elaborate on the prospective benefits of B2G data sharing, we adopted the conceptualization of value from Austin & Seitanidi who discussed four types of value: associational, transferred resource, interactional, and synergistic value.

3. METHODS

This research was designed as a case study with embedded subcases and was performed in interpretive fashion (Yin, 2018; Walsham, 1995). The case that was empirically studied is Statistics Netherlands (CBS), which has a history of collaborations with private organisations on data sharing. Two subcases were studied as part of this embedded case study. Subcase I concerned the sharing of transport data from several transportation companies to CBS in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Subcase II concerned the sharing of payment data from payment service providers, also in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The case study research was based on analysis of relevant documentation (internal documents, policies, communications etc.) and on semi-structured interviews (twelve in total) with respondents from CBS and private sector partners in each subcase. The interviews were analysed through a thematic analysis using semi-open coding.

4. KEY FINDINGS

The case study research concluded that both public and private organisations engaging in B2G data sharing are driven by a **mix of organisational self-interest and societal motivations**. For statistics agencies, self-interest can be manifested in improved statistics and methodologies. Whereas, for the private sector the prospective organisational gains, as the case studies showed, can be gaining business intelligence.

This research proposed **two mechanisms** to align the interests of public and private organisations to create mutual benefits in voluntary B2G data sharing partnerships. First, based on the results it can be argued that **finding and building on linked interests**, which connects the self-interest of organisations to create societal value, was essential to form the partnerships in the subcases. *Urgency* is considered as a key alignment mechanism in the two cases in the context of COVID-19, as this created a common ground on which the partnership could build. Urgency as an alignment mechanism can have implications for future voluntary B2G data sharing partnerships in addressing societal challenges. Furthermore, the *identification of a partner's needs, goals, and perception* of the partnership is identified as a mechanism to find and build on linked interests, as well as *establishing and maintaining intensive contact* with private partners. These two alignment mechanisms can help government organisations to identify potential value propositions for the private sector partners and establish trust

The second proposed alignment mechanism was the **provision of incentives**. This research identified three categories of incentives and rewards: *data reciprocity* (e.g. returning data to the data holder), *knowledge sharing* (e.g. knowledge on data processing and analysing methods), and *cost reductions for data holders* (e.g. quid pro quo agreement). These are considered to be promising in creating win-win situations in voluntary B2G data sharing partnerships.

With regards to **benefits and value of B2G data sharing**, this research contends that B2G data sharing for societal challenges can create various types of value, yet our analyses identified mainly *transferred resource* (e.g., more frequent publication of statistics and business intelligence) and *interactional* values (e.g., new and/or improved methodologies).

Fig. 1 presents the extended theoretical framework derived from Rukanova et. al and elaborated based on this research findings.

Figure 1: Extended framework for voluntary B2G data sharing based on the case findings.

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